

**THE IMPROVEMENT OF READ ALOUD ABILITY BY USING
WORD CARD MEDIA OF SECOND GRADE STUDENTS
IN SDN 1 PAJANG No. 93 SURAKARTA, INDONESIA
ACADEMIC YEAR 2016/2017**

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Abstract:

One important aspect of Bahasa Indonesia teaching in elementary role is reading, especially read aloud. Bahasa Indonesia learning geared to improve the ability of learners to communicate in Bahasa Indonesia properly, whether oral or written, create appreciation of human literacy in Indonesia. Indonesian language learning according to the author's experiences during this time by verbal learning, students just listen to teachers lecturing from day to day and it make students bore. This situation can be resolved by creating fun and friendly teaching and learning activities. Teachers, in delivering the material, can use word card. The delivery of learning, especially in Bahasa Indonesia needs strategy to increase the ability of the 2nd grade students especially in read aloud a simple sentence. This strategy can be done through observation of concrete objects, using simple examples in real life, using simple language, conducted in interesting and fun situations, so that children are motivated and not easily bored. With the application of such methods, it is expected to improve the ability to read aloud of 2nd grade students in SDN Pajang 1 No. 93. The researchers used a qualitative approach of classroom action research type. The result of this study shows an increase in the ability to read aloud by average score of 68.6 with 100% pass. The result of the evaluation of Cycle II shows the study achievement study until 100%. It is proven that the method of word card in loud reading is suitable to enhance reading skills of 2nd grade students at SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta.

Keywords: ability, read aloud, word card, Bahasa learning

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1. Research Background

The development of language proficiency has a central role in the development of intellectual, social, emotional and learners and supporting aspect in successful learning. Bahasa Indonesia learning geared to improve the ability of learners to communicate in Bahasa Indonesia well, orally or written, as well as create appreciation of human literacy in Indonesia.

This is in line with the opinion of K. Goodman about the concept of language ability that can be seen in two sides, namely: alignment of language material in language learning and the alignment of material of the language with other subjects. The changes is not only viewed from the communicative approach of student-centered learning, but learning resources, time allocation and evaluation that are not found in the outlines of learning program (GBPP) will provide teachers to create the learning program. This is supported by language skills.

As the curriculum of KTSP 2006, Bahasa Indonesia learning objective is that learners have the ability as follows:

- 1) communicate effectively and efficiently in accordance with the applicable ethics, whether oral or written;
- 2) to appreciate and be proud of using Bahasa Indonesia as a language of unity;
- 3) understanding Bahasa Indonesia and use them appropriately and creatively for a variety of purposes;
- 4) using Bahasa Indonesia to enhance intellectual ability, as well as social and emotional maturity;
- 5) enjoy and use literature to expand insight, manners, and to improve the knowledge and language proficiency;
- 6) respect Indonesia literacy as a literary treasure of the cultural and intellectual of Indonesia;

Student learning outcomes are influenced by several factors from either within its own students as well as factors from outside in the form of learning methods applied by the teachers. According to Purwanto (2002) there are two main factors that influence the results of the study i.e. from inside (internal) and from the outside (external). Factors in the organism itself referred to individual factors, and there are factors outside of individuals referred to as social factors. Factors included in the individual factor are growth of maturity, intelligence, training, motivation, and personal factors. Factors included in the social factor are family, neighbourhood, opportunity available and social motivation, teachers and how they teach, as well as the media used in teaching and learning.

The difficulties of student learners can lead students tend to be passive, students are only able to replicate when told to imitate by the teacher, students are only able to designate when told to shows by the teacher. Students are only able to do something when there is an order from a teacher and must be guided by the teacher. According to Choiri and Yusuf (2008) that "*children who have physical traits and appearance of late speech/language development, with the characteristics: (1) the dysfunction in general intelligence or below average, (2) an inability in adaptive behavior and (3) development occurred until the age of 18 years*".

In teaching and learning children with barriers in reading, it takes the suitable learning media. One alternative learning media that are considered appropriate to enhance the ability of read aloud a simple sentence of the second grade students is by using card. The use of suitable media or tools is one way to provide a meaningful experience and forming an understanding of students. The selection of the right media by teachers is expected to assist students in understanding the material presented.

Word card media is a graphical word media directly involve the sense of vision. Word card has the pictures stimulus as well as word stimulus at once, so that the use of this visual media can facilitate students in understanding the information. The card of the word or phrase is used as a medium in game contest speech (say or pronounce). The pronunciation of the words can be expanded in the form of sentence. The important things of using word card is to train students pronouncing the language sounds (vowels, consonants, dialogue, and cluster) in accordance with the articulation.

2. Research Methods

This research is characterized by the presence of continuous improvement until it reaches the achievement of its goals. The revisions are done on each cycle. PTK is characterized by continuous improvements.

PTK is practical, situational, and conditional based on the problems in school. This type of research offers new models, approaches, strategies and procedures which are more effective. PTK should be fixed on things happening in the classroom.

This research is a problem-solving activity that starts from: planning (planning), implementation (action), data collection (observing), analyze the data or information to decide the extent to which the advantages or weakness of the action (reflecting).

The subject of this study is students of 2nd grade SDN Pajang I no. 93. The subject is 7 slow learners of 2nd grade. The research was carried out collaboratively between students and teachers/observer to collect and gather data objectively. Research activities conducted in the first semester.

The aspects that will be examined in this study include children's reading skills and motivation and creativity of children's learning both individually and group. The criteria used to measure the level of success in this research is if there is an increase in students' ability in reading as well as their interest of learning in the classroom. In minimum, students can reach standard score (KKM).

Data collected is described and then analysed and compared the results of each cycle with the indicators of success. Critical analysis of the results shows the advantages and disadvantages of performance students and teachers in the process of learning to read aloud using word card.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the results of the implementation of read aloud learning material using word card, it can be served the result in the form of table.

Table 4.1: The ability to Read Aloud of 2nd Grade in SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 of Surakarta

No	Initial	Score	Explanation
1	A	65	Pass
2	B	55	Remidial
3	C	45	Remidial
4	D	55	Remidial
5	E	65	Pass
6	F	50	Remidial
7	G	55	Remidial
	Total	390	
	Mean	55,71	
	Percentage	28,5%	Remidial

Read aloud ability at the first condition can be drawn in the form of graphic as follows.

In the graphic above, the students' score indicates that 5 students scored below 65. There are 2 students scored 65 or more. As it known, 65 is minimum score to pass according to KTSP 2006. Thus there are 5 children who have not reached KKM. These data indicate that learning read aloud material at 2nd grade II SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta has not met the limit completely. Thus, on this condition, read aloud material has not achieved the expected goals.

Based on the low read aloud ability, teacher should try to create innovation in learning so it can be improved. Learning innovation is done by using word card said to increase the activity read aloud ability of students.

Based on the results of the implementation of the actions, the ability to read aloud using word card on cycle I can be presented in the following table:

Table 4.2: The ability to Read Aloud Grade II SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta Cycle I

No	Initial	Score	Explanation
1	A	75	Pass
2	B	65	Pass
3	C	60	Remidial
4	D	65	Pass
5	E	70	Pass
6	F	60	Remidial
7	G	60	Remidial
	Total	455	
	Mean	65	
	Percentage	57,1%	Remidial

Read aloud ability on cycle I can be drawn in the form of graphic as follows.

The students score above shows that 4 students scored 65 or more. While the students, who scored under 65, there are 3 students. The average score is 57,1%. This data shows that learning to read aloud on 2nd grade in SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta has not met the limit completely. Thus, the cycle I can be concluded that it has not achieved the expected goals and needs to be continued at the next cycle.

The ability to speak loud on the first conditions is known to be the lowest score (45) and the highest score (65). Increasing ability to speak loud using word cards on cycle I create the lowest score as 55 and the highest score 70. 4 students scored 65 or more, while 3 students scored below 65. The average score is 65, so it needs to be continued at the cycle II.

Based on the results of the observations above, it can be known that students cannot use time well. To follow up, learning cycle II need to be emphasized on the importance of students' utilization of time.

Based on the results of the implementation on the cycle II, loud reading skills using word cards on Cycle II can be presented in the following table:

Table 4.3: Read Aloud Ability of 2nd grade students in SDN Pajang I No. 93, Surakarta

No	Initial	Score	Explanation
1	A	75	Pass
2	B	70	Pass
3	C	70	Pass
4	D	65	Pass
5	E	70	Pass
6	F	65	Pass
7	G	65	Pass
	Total	480	
	Mean	68,6	
	Percentage	100%	Pass

In table 4.3 above, the score of the students shows that all students reach score of 65 or more. The average score is 70 with the percentage reaches 100%. This data shows that the ability to read aloud on a grade II SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta have reached minimum score.

In Cycle I, loud speaking ability is known that the lowest score is 60 and the highest score is 70. In cycle II there is an enhancement of speak aloud ability by using word card. In cycle II is known that the lowest score is 65 and the highest score is 75. 7 students reach score of 65 or more. The score of the average is 68.6 and the percentage reaches 100%, so the action research was stopped.

Based on the observation above, it is known that students can use proper time better than on cycle II. Students are enthusiast to do read aloud activity and they are brave to ask the teacher.

Table 4.4: Score of Read Aloud Ability in Every Cycle

No	Initial	First	Cycle I	Cycle II
1	A	65	75	75
2	B	55	65	70
3	C	45	60	70
4	D	55	65	65
5	E	65	70	70
6	F	50	60	65
7	G	55	60	65
Total		440	455	480
Mean		62,9	65	68,6
Percentage		28,6%	57,1%	100%

The improvement of read aloud ability from the table above can be presented in the form of graphic as follows.

Based on the average score of each cycle of loud reading skills using word cards media, it can be made as follows:

Cycles	Average Score	Improvement
First	62,9	0
Cycle I	65	2,1
Cycle II	68,6	3,6

Improvement of ability to read aloud grade II SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta using word cards can be described in the form of a graph as follows:

Based on the results from cycle II, it shows that the average value of loud reading skills have reached 68.6 from 7 students. 100% students scored 65 or more indicates that this cycle has been completed.

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the use of word card can improve the ability to read aloud of 2nd grade students in SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 Surakarta academic year 2016/2017. The results shows that word card can improve the ability to read aloud. So the hypothesis "*the use of word card can improve the ability of read aloud on 2nd grade in SDN Pajang I academic year 2016/2017*" is accepted.

Word card media has benefits namely, to clarify the presentation of the message so that it is not too verbally, overcoming the limitations of space, time, and memory, raises the excitement of learning; allows more direct interaction between the student and the environment and reality, lets students learn individually according to ability and his interest.

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the use of word card media can improve the ability to read aloud of 2nd grade in SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 of Surakarta. This media can be good things to increased ability to read aloud for students. Word card gives benefit for the child in second class, make it easier for students to remember the meaning of the words on the card, and it will make easier to develop words or stories or new idea. The teacher realizes that by reducing verbal descriptions on the word cards, its benefits will be showed, especially for 2nd grade in SDN Pajang 1 No. 93 of Surakarta in learning read aloud.

4. Conclusion

Based on the research results above, it can be concluded that use of the word card media in learning Bahasa Indonesia with loud reading materials can improve the reading skills of students. This is because students learn by concrete media and various learning atmosphere. This is in contrast to the previous system of learning where students just listen to teachers lecturing from day to day and make students feel bored.

5. Suggestion

For students, they should be more creative in improving their reading skills by using word card media both at home and school. While for teachers, they can use word cards in improving the reading skills of their students so that boredom in studying can be avoided.

References

1. Choiri, A.S, Yusuf, M. 2008. Pendidikan Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus Secara Inklusif. Surakarta: FKIP UNS
2. Nurhadi. 2008. Membaca Cepat dan Efektif. Bandung : Sinar Baru Algensindo
3. Nurman. 2010. Meningkatkan kemampuan Baca Tulis Bahasa Indonesia. <http://www.justnurman.wordpress.com> diakses Juli 2016.
4. Zuhdi, D & Budiasih. 2007. Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Bahasa Indonesia di Kelas Rendah. Yogyakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional.

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